

TEACHING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN TO CARRY OUT SIMPLE EXPERIMENTS IN NATURE

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the nature, the events that occur in it, the laws of nature play an important role in the formation of a child's personality, and the young people are brought up intellectually, aesthetically, physically, and in the spirit of nature protection.

Nature, its events, natural laws play an important role in the formation of a child's personality, young people are brought up intellectually, aesthetically, physically, and in the spirit of nature protection as they get to know them.

In the process of introducing preschool children to nature, great attention is paid to forming a careful attitude towards nature.

In order to educate young people in this spirit, first of all, the future specialists who are studying in universities and pedagogic schools should understand the nature, necessity, and task of introducing them to nature. They will acquire this in the process of reading and learning this course.

The purpose of the course is to help young people, who are conscious builders of the new society, to acquire excellent knowledge about nature, to get acquainted with the methods of growing plants, animal care, and most importantly, if they can observe nature and see its beauty, then they will be careful about nature and is to educate caring attitude. Students' love for nature, our dear country, Motherland is formed on this basis.

The main task of the course is to acquaint children with existing methods, best practices, historical materials, and theoretical knowledge.

Especially in the current period of reconstruction in our country, it is necessary to better organize the independent work of students, to increase their activity in this important work. Currently, a wide range of issues related to the spiritual, moral and aesthetic education of students and educators is emerging. We are living in a turning point.

Educational institutions of pre-school education also have their own programs and methods of introducing children to nature. Every student should master it completely. It is impossible to carry out the educational process there without knowing the program and teaching methods of the countries of knowledge.

Also, students should learn new work experiences in the field of introducing children to nature in existing non-governmental educational institutions. They learn this during their internships in non-state educational institutions, they record the information they need. The most important thing is how children are introduced to nature in non-governmental educational institutions, how the classrooms are equipped, the methods of organizing the nature corner in each age group, how correct or incorrect they are. they learn about it. For this, they use the existing "program". This program is the main performance criterion for every preschool student. Only every educator can make additions to it, taking into account his own conditions, his non-state educational institution, environmental conditions.

Today's student is tomorrow's expert. Therefore, the demands placed on current students are even greater. Because our time, our life is always developing. In the field of science and technology, in the field of education and training, new and new aspects are opening, and we experts should have mastered and learned all of them. Otherwise, we lack a mature specialist. It is necessary for employees of pre-school educational institutions to constantly improve their knowledge. From time to time, in order to increase their knowledge, they study in specially organized training courses to familiarize themselves with new methods, forms and methods of education.

In training courses, classes on the method of introducing educators to nature are held based on lecture, conversation, story methods. They strengthen each lesson they have heard through practical exercises. They practice in pre-school educational institutions and conduct training on the basis of the "Children's Pre-School Education Program". They learn the methods and methods of introduction to nature.

The purpose of the course on the methodology of introducing preschool education employees to nature in the training courses is to familiarize educators and employees with new knowledge and concepts about nature, with innovations created in the field of nature, with achievements in the field of science and technology, and to increase their qualifications and skills in this field. The development of the child's body starts from birth. This means intensive, very rapid development of sense organs and perception. Thanks to these sense organs and perception, he sees and feels the surrounding things, smell, shape, its bigness and smallness, music, sound, color. He thinks about them. Eyes, ears, nose, and skin enter the sense organs, and they are the means of seeing, hearing, smelling, tasting, skin, and movement, and their perceptions are the means of knowing life. Children's mental development depends on the development of these sense organs and perceptions. This is also the result of sensory education.

So, what is sensory education? The term "sensor" is derived from the Latin word "sensus" - "feeling", "intuition", "perception", "sensing ability". Sensory education is a part of mental education, which means the appropriate development and improvement of the child's sensory organs and perceptions.

The more rich and well-developed intuition and perception are, the faster a person can understand the surrounding events in nature, and the more extensive and versatile his knowledge about them is.

It is known that during the development of social labor for many centuries, the human society has compacted, sensed and perceived the external stimuli that affect a person (as a result of various external influences, external environment, living conditions).

The role of nature in the development of a child's mind and sensory education is incomparably great. It is not surprising that the formation and development of intuition and perception in the human body was directly influenced by nature. Imagine that in the period of the early primitive society when man was first formed, that is, in the period of the first development of the ape, as a result of the struggle for survival, these senses and perception abilities were developed in the human body. At that time, people had to find food to live. This is their ability to see (to see the distance, to see the opposite creature, animal, to be able to distinguish between them), to hear (to avoid external enemies, to hear the movement of hunting animals in the surrounding, nearby ground for hunting, to hear the sound of birds), the ability to taste (knowing whether the food is sweet or bitter, hot or cold, poisonous or non-poisonous with the help of the tongue), the ability to smell (to know whether the food smells or not, whether there is food nearby), movement (to find food from the prey created the ability to run, run away to avoid the enemy, move quickly to do the work).

Therefore, the emergence and development of intuition and perception, which is formed in the human body and is important in the formation of a person, is a biological process. This process is the most important in the education of today's young people through the means of nature. , cow, dog, cat, horse, donkey, goat, etc.), their appearance, body structure, skin covered with wool, their behavior, running, walking, making sounds greatly affect the development of the child's intuition and perception.

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